

DJANGO FRAMEWORK PLANFORMASI BILAN TANISHISH VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI

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Anotatsiya: Django framework planformasi Python dasturlash tili uchun yaratilgan veb-dasturlash framework'idir. Django framework planformasi veb-dasturlarni tezkor va xavfsiz ishlab chiqishga yordam beradi. Django framework planformasi "Batteries included" falsafasini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi va veb-dasturlash uchun kerakli bo'lgan barcha funksiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Django framework planformasi MVT (Model View Template) dizayn shabloniga asoslanadi va ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan ishlash uchun Object Relational Mapping (ORM) usulini qo'llaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Django , python, modellar, html

Veb-dasturlash sohasida Python dasturlash tili keng tarqalgan va oson ishlatiladigan dasturlash tillaridan biridir. Python dasturlash tili uchun yaratilgan veb-dasturlash framework'lari ham mavjud, ular orasida Django framework planformasi eng mashhur va qulay bo'lganlardan hisoblanadi. Django framework planformasi veb-dasturlarni tezkor va xavfsiz ishlab chiqishga yordam beradi. Django framework planformasi "Batteries included" falsafasini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi va veb-dasturlash uchun kerakli bo'lgan barcha funksiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Django framework planformasi MVT (Model View Template) dizayn shabloniga asoslanadi va ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan ishlash uchun Object Relational Mapping (ORM) usulini qo'llaydi. Bu matnda biz Django framework planformasini qanday o'rnatish va uning asosiy imkoniyatlarini qanday ishlatishni ko'rib chiqamiz.

Django framework planformasini o'rnatish uchun quyidagi bosqichlarni amalga oshiramiz:

Python dasturlash tilini o'rnatamiz. Django framework planformasi Python dasturlash tiliga bog'liq bo'lgani uchun, avval Python dasturlash tilini o'rnatishimiz kerak. Python dasturlash tilining eng so'nggi versiyasini quyidagi havoladan yuklab olishimiz mumkin: <https://www.python.org/downloads/>

Pip paket boshqaruvchisini o'rnatamiz. Pip paket boshqaruvchisi Python uchun yaratilgan kutubxonalarni o'rnatish va boshqarish uchun mo'ljallangan vositadir. Pip paket boshqaruvchisi Python dasturlash tilining yangi versiyalarida avtomatik ravishda o'rnatiladi, lekin agar sizda pip paket

boshqaruvchisi mavjud bo'lmasa, quyidagi havoladan yuklab olishingiz mumkin:
<https://pip.pypa.io/en/stable/installation/>

Django framework planformasini o'rnatamiz. Django framework planformasini pip paket boshqaruvchisi yordamida osonlik bilan o'rnatishimiz mumkin.

Buning uchun terminalda quyidagi buyruqni kiriting: `pip install django`

Yangi Django loyihasini yaratamiz. Django framework planformasini o'rnatgandan so'ng, yangi Django loyihasini yaratishimiz mumkin. Buning uchun terminalda quyidagi buyruqni kiriting: `django-admin startproject projectname`
 Bu buyruq `projectname` deb nomlangan yangi papkani yaratadi va uning ichida Django loyihasining asosiy fayllari bo'ladi.

Yangi Django ilovasini yaratamiz. Django loyihasi bir nechta Django ilovalaridan iborat bo'lishi mumkin. Django ilovasi loyiha ichidagi alohida bir moduldir, u o'ziga xos modellar, ko'rinishlar, shablonlar va boshqa fayllarni o'z ichiga oladi. Yangi Django ilovasini yaratish uchun terminalda quyidagi buyruqni kiriting: `python manage.py startapp appname`
 Bu buyruq `appname` deb nomlangan yangi papkani yaratadi va uning ichida Django ilovasining asosiy fayllari bo'ladi.

Django framework planformasining asosiy imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish uchun quyidagi bosqichlarni amalga oshiramiz:

Modellar bilan ishlash. Modellar ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan ishlash uchun kerakli sinflardir, ular ma'lumotlar bazasidagi jadvalning strukturasi va xususiyatlarini aks ettiradi. Modellar orqali biz ma'lumotlar bazasida jadval yaratish, jadvalga ma'lumot qo'shish, jadvaldan ma'lumot olish, jadvalni o'zgartirish yoki o'chirish kabi amallarni bajarishimiz mumkin. Modellar `models.py` faylida joylashgan.

Ko'rinishlar bilan ishlash. Ko'rinishlar mijozdan kelgan so'rovni qabul qiluvchi va javob beruvchi funksiyalardir, ular modellardan ma'lumotlarni talab qiladi va shablonlarga jo'natadi. Ko'rinishlar `views.py` faylida joylashgan.

Shablonlar bilan ishlash. Shablonlar veb-sahifaning ko'rinishini tasvirlaydigan fayllardir, ular HTML kodlari va Django teglaridan iborat bo'ladi¹. Shablonlar orqali biz ma'lumotlarni dinamik ravishda ko'rsatishimiz mumkin. Shablonlar `templates` papkasida joylashgan.

URL-lar bilan ishlash. URL-lar veb-sahifalarning manzillaridir, ular mijozning so'roviga mos ko'rinishni tanlashga yordam beradi. URL-lar `urls.py` faylida joylashgan.

Quyidagi kodda biz Django framework planformasi yordamida oddiy veb-sahifa yaratamiz:

```
# models.py fayli
```

```
from django.db import models
```

Person modelini yaratamiz

```
class Person(models.Model):
    name = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    age = models.IntegerField()
```

```
def __str__(self):
    return self.name
```

views.py fayli

```
from django.shortcuts import render
from .models import Person
```

index ko'rinishini yaratamiz

```
def index(request):
    # Person modelidan barcha obyektlarni olamiz
    people = Person.objects.all()
    # index.html shabloniga people ro'yxatini jo'natamiz
    return render(request, "index.html", {"people": people})
```

templates/index.html fayli

```
<h1>People List</h1>
<ul>
{% for person in people %}
    <li>{{ person.name }} - {{ person.age }}</li>
{% endfor %}
</ul>
```

urls.py fayli

```
from django.urls import path
from . import views
```

```
urlpatterns = [
    # index ko'rinishi uchun URL-ni belgilaymiz
    path("", views.index, name="index"),
```

]

Bu kodni ishga tushirsak, bizning veb-sahifamizda Person modelidan olgan ma'lumotlarni ro'yxat shaklida ko'rinishimiz mumkin.

Xulosa

Bu matnda biz Django framework planformasini qanday o'rnatish va uning asosiy imkoniyatlarini qanday ishlatishni ko'rib chiqdik. Biz modellar, ko'rinishlar, shablonlar va URL-lar bilan ishlashni namoyon etdik. Biz ham oddiy veb-sahifa yaratdik.

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